
Introduction to Genetic Parallel Deep Thinking and Reasonomics

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Abstract

In light of Google's Deep Thinking approach becoming available for public usage for their Gemini 2.5 model, we propose a bio-inspired genetic algorithm like systematic approach to reasoning dubbed **Genetic Parallel Deep Thinking** 'GPDT' and the related concept of a **reasonome**. We primarily focus on use of the GPDT, which uses approach uses a natural selection inspired approach to generating and refining solutions, in testable environments (algorithmic time complexity). Crucial to this concept of GPDT is another novel idea named a reasonome, which is a modular genome made up of reasoning logic units that define approaches to problem solving. Additionally, we discuss the scientific concepts behind these ideas, propose a genetic algorithm system using the GPDT reasoning approach, discuss the ramifications a technique of this sort could have on the area of Human-AI collaboration, and finally layout next steps for future research.

Keywords

Genetic algorithms, reasoning strategies, large language models, 'deep' parallel thinking, self-play, horizontal gene transfer, time complexity

1 Introduction

Recently at the time of writing, Google released a "deep thinking" feature for its Gemini model on August 1st 2025 to the public. A model with this ability was able to achieve a gold medal in the International Mathematical Olympiad of which only 8% of contestants achieve this merit (Luong and Lockhart, 2025). Their setup enables a model to simultaneously explore and combine multiple possible solutions before giving a final answer. This is opposed to choosing a single linear chain of thought seen in other commercially available models. Early users of deep thinking models report amazing results and high levels of satisfaction with many saying that is is the current top standard for reasoning approaches. It may be too soon to tell, but this innovation may lead to similar explorations of parallel thinking approaches in the AI model arena as there has already been movement in the direction towards models with advanced reasoning abilities caused by the diminishing returns of traditional LLMs (Science, 2025).

Although we have not personally tested out this feature here at Grandma's Boy Labs, this reasoning strategy first made us think of Doctor Strange. However, then we thought of a system that also compares solutions in parallel better than any known computer, **mother nature** and more pointedly **evolution**. For example, think of a large spawning of tadpoles in a murky swamp all from two parents who's genomes have been mixed and mingled. Each one of these tadpoles' small variations is an exploration of a precise combination of codes put through a cosmic quality control process to see if even a small change leads to an improvement. Now consider expanding the idea to

include each tadpole in the swamp. The fierce pressure for resources while developing and eventually mating causes the pressure towards more 'fit' solutions to be even more intense. This is the essence of evolutionary pressure in populations, which is driven to find increasingly more fit solutions for environments.

Here at Grandma's Boy Lab, we are proposing applying these evolutionary concepts to the parallel deep thinking approach described by Google to large language models as an alternative approach to more rigid/expertly tuned reasoning systems. We take inspiration not only from Google's deep thinking concept, but also their other computational methods used to arrive at better solutions to mathematical and infrastructure problems (Lee et al., 2025). We are dubbing this approach 'Genetic Parallel Deep Thinking' 'GPDT'. In GPDT, *modular reasoning units* (induction, abduction, causal inference, etc) would make up the *genotype* and the reasoning logic in action (or behavior) could be considered the *phenotype*. We hypothesize that such an approach would enable a team to not only automatically arrive at solutions to complex problems, but also explore and study the nature of reasoning habits as they adapt to problems. We take inspiration from nature in our exploration of this idea by using the concept of genomes to track reasoning combinations and proposed solutions.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce and explain hypothetical frameworks for this concept of GPDT thought of by lead scientist of Grandma's Boy Lab: Emmitt J Tucker.

Our process will go as follows:

1. Go over the scientific inspirations that lead to arriving at these ideas.
2. Introduce the concept of a reasoning genome or 'reasonome'.
3. Explain four novel genetic algorithm applications to large language model deep thinking parallelism.
4. Discuss the hypothetical implications of these and other genetic inspired deep thinking approaches to Human-AI companionship landscape.
5. Go over next steps in the this line of research.

2 Background and Inspirations

2.1 Scientific

- **Recursive Self-Improvement:** Describes a system that can improve its own abilities and then use those improved abilities to further enhance itself, creating a feedback loop that can lead to rapid and significant advancements. In theory this would look like an AI model that can modify its own source code(Contributors, 2025c). GPDT takes inspiration form this idea of a system capable of improving itself over time with limited to no human intervention.
- **Parallel Processing/Multi-threading:** This method allows for computers to make computations in parallel within a single program which can speed up results in certain situations(Contributors, 2025b). GPDT uses this idea to define the multiple angles to solutions considered in this approach. The increased popularity of GPUs has made this approach to problem solving more popular, especially with LLM use.

- **Bacterial Transformation:** Horizontal gene transfer 'HGT' allows for genetic flow within individuals of the same generation. This occurs in some types of bacteria. HGT can occur one when individual latches onto another with an appendage and sends a portion of their DNA over. This can also occur when a bacteria dies and other bacteria are able to pick up (possibly useful) remnants of their genome (Contributors, 2025a). This phenomena has been studied thoroughly, and is believed to allow prokaryotic organisms to quickly adapt to their environment which is why there is a growing concern surrounding antibiotic resistance (M et al., 2020).
- **Genetic Algorithms 'GA' (particularly the life cycle and microbial variations):** In these heuristic approaches solutions are organized into genomes/genes that go through an initialization, ranking, selection, and reproduction for a predefined period or until a satisfactory solution is reached. The life cycle variations can include giving the solutions different behaviors based on their stage of life and or diversifying the population's 'phase' demographics (Felix-Saul et al., 2024). Microbial versions of genetic algorithms are inspired by microbe communities and include the principals of HGT (Harvey, 2011).

2.2 Fictional/Media

- **Naruto (Anime/Manga):** A technique featured in the show allows the main character to make clones of himself to aid him with tasks, from the mundane to combat. When one of these clones vanishes, its memories clone are dispersed throughout the remaining clone network. GPDT takes inspiration from the 'collective memory' of the clones in this work of fiction combined with the phenomenon of horizontal gene transfer.
- **Doctor Strange (Comic books/Movies):** During the climactic battle with the purple villain Thanos, Doctor Strange was able to use the time stone to simultaneously consider trillions of different possible outcomes of their battle. We talk inspiration from this concept when discussing the role of personalized super intelligence and Transhumanism.
- **Super Meat Boy (Video Game):** In this platforming game, after completing a level, you are able to see all of your sprites run across the screen showing all failed attempts at finding a solution. We take inspiration from this end of level screen, with a competitive and genetic inspired twist.

3 Introducing the 'Reasonome'

3.1 The Concept

The **reasonome** is a concept we are purposing in addition to GPDT that is critical to the functioning of this hypothesis and concept. The simplest way to imagine it a circular plasmid DNA vector but it could also work in more complex genome organizational structures reminiscent of eukaryotes. The reasonome is a combination of cognitive reasoning techniques that forms a cognitive strategy. These plasmids are designed for insertion into microbial agents in conceptual digital evolutionary simulation framework. A simple agent would be a single entity that has a **Reasoning Nucleus** made up of a collection of reasonomes (cognitive strategies). Within the reasoning nucleus, the different reasonomes can exchange modular units. The proposed plasmids should allow for adaptive problem solving, abstract thought, and dynamic inference across variety environments. A single agent could have dozens to billions of different reasonomes

within their reasoning nucleus depending on the available hardware and compute resources.

3.2 Organization Detail and Functions

The hypothetical plasmid we propose has a circular shape, enabling continuous traversal and flexible insertion. For simplicity, our proposed plasmid will have 12-20 reasoning operons composed of **reasonotides** (reasoning nucleotides) of varying length. In theory, space complexity would increase with the size of the plasmid, meaning that memory resources would be a limiting factor in this approach. We theorize that plasmids of a larger size would allow individual reasonomes to form more complex reactions to the problems they encounter.

- **Origin of Replication 'ORI'**: Defines when and how reasoning gets triggered in the agent's life cycle, usually caused by pressure of cognitive load. For example, the ORI could be triggered when the agent encounters a problem of a particular variety (example: long division). This problem stimuli could cause the agent to enter a state that is optimized to quickly solve the problems of that given variety and dynamically respond to encountered problems.
- **Promoter/Repressor**: Regulatory regions that control which reasoning modules get expressed. For example, a promoter could cause more 'induction' genes to be expressed. We believe this would potentially increase the model's adaptive abilities. In this context, regions would be activated by uncertainty, increase/decrease expensive reasoning under limited resources, adjust expression levels of modules based on successful reasoning attempts.
- **Modular Operons**: The core reasoning genes that is a tightly linked cluster of related techniques. These genes encode different code types of cognitive logic (deduction, induction, abduction, etc). The expression of these units could look like the model using a given sequence of logical investigations when exploring a problem. It could also look like a fusion of logical approaches for a given unit being expressed.
- **Intron**: The non-coding regions of the genome that do not play a part in reasoning logic. These are important for preserving population and through genome rearrangement these genes can become active.
- **Epigenetic Modulation (Not Explored)**: This was not explored due to the unconfirmed nature of epigenetics and the increased computational complexity it would add to the system without potentially making the biological microbial model more realistic.
- **Epigenetic Transposons (Not Explored)**: These regions would allow for the individual reasonome exchange modular sequence locations. This was not explored due to the increased computational complexity it could add to the system with perhaps no benefit.

Reference figure 1 for a drawing of this conceptual reasonome.

3.3 Simple Model Agent within a Genetic Algorithm

We propose a microbial inspired AI agent that can process our proposed reasonome. This proposed agent will contain 5-8 reasonomes to keep things on a small scale. For

simplicity, we will explain how this would work with algorithmic time complexity for example starting from a preexisting testable coding solution to a problem on a platform like leetcode.com. We are choosing time complexity because it has a machine confirmable result (increase/decrease in performance time or failure in execution) within code interpreter (example: python3), which could guide future experiment planning. Therefore, the imaginary agents refereed to when talking about the time complexity use case would be competitive programming agents designed to attempt to find better solutions to algorithm problems. We are drawing inspiration from the paper on Absolute-Zero Learning which also used a machine testable environment to develop a system that was able to learn with much less training data than seen in other methods (Zhao et al., 2025).

Within a genetic algorithm, these agents would spawn with a randomized genome with a population of potential reasoning strategies. **This population of strategies would go through the following phases:**

1. **Initialization:** In this step, the initial population of reasoning strategies is spawned. The population could be spawned completely at random, or with variations of a predefined and potentially previously successful strategy (example: working code example within the best known time complexity). A predefined population size of agents would be spawned as well depending on the framework used (described below). If there is more than one agent to host a reasoning nucleus, the reasoning strategies would be equally divided within the individuals in the population. The result would be a single AI model with a population of different reasonomes embedded in its reasoning nucleus. In our time complexity example this would look like making small variations to an existing programming solution to get a time complexity of a certain magnitude (example: $O(n)$). Depending on the variation of the spawning, most of the reasonome solutions should be within similar time complexity magnitudes. However, there should hypothetically be the possibility that even a small change in decreasing the time complexity could helpful for a use case.
2. **Testing/Life Cycle:** The agent population's individual reasoning nuclei goes through a series of tests based on their reasoning task/objective. In our time complexity example, this could look like putting each reasoning strategies resulting coding solution through a test suite and ranking them based on their average performance. This phase simulates the individual agent's life cycle. During this time, reasonomes within the reasoning nucleus freely exchange tactics. This would be akin to a open/shared notes test on a given assignment with individual grades.
3. **Selection:** A variety of different existing selection strategies could be used. In this paper, we will stick to the idea of roulette wheel selection, where the likelihood of being chose for a round of reproduction is determined by test performance. Using this strategy, the more successful reasonomes are more likely to be selected for reproduction and the population is more likely to converge on a better solution in terms of speed.
4. **Reproduction:** The different reasoning strategies are shuffled according to reproductive operators (crossover and mutation). This produces new solutions and will hopefully lead to more fit individuals as the generations of the reasoning nucleus progress. Shuffling could be taken a step further by also shuffling reasonomes

across agents via selection mating, but that is not covered in the scope of this paper.

5. **Repeat steps 2-4:** The new population is tested, and goes through the selection and reproduction process until a satisfactory result (defined by the user) is reached.
6. **Termination:** Once a satisfactory solution is reached, the simulation would end, returning the model 'Reasonomics'. These Reasonomics can be used to investigate and recreate the model if deemed useful.

Key Differences from a standard GA:

1. Ideas reproduce, not agents themselves (in this exploration).
2. Termination condition varies depending on framework used (described below).
3. The population is WITHIN the agent, so technically this simulation could occur with a single agent.

A depiction of the life cycle of the reasonomes is shown in figure 2 within the thought bubble.

4 Four Novel Approaches to Genetic Inspired Parallel Deep Thinking

We have developed 4 conceptual frameworks to apply GPDT to individual model development. Models developed in these frameworks could be used to potentially create more powerful systems through ensemble approaches, but further exploration of that concept is not covered here.

1. **Framework 1 - Basic (Single-Model) GPDT:** This framework involves a single agent model, with it's own attempts to come up with better ideas within it's own reasoning nucleus when faced with a given problem. The single model's reasoning nucleus goes through a similar genetic algorithm process described above. After each generation, model's reasoning nucleus will be profiled to see if a satisfactory reasoning strategy was made. Success will result in termination of the simulation, while failure will continue to GPDT process. A concept drawing of this framework can be found in figure 2. In this drawing, note that the problem has a condition that MUST be satisfied for it to be considered solved (like a decrease in time complexity). For the time complexity example, this would look like trying to test a plethora of different algorithmic 'solutions' to a given problem, logging and ranking each result and checking for a satisfactory solution (in terms of speed) each generation. If there are multiple superior solutions within one nucleus, the best performing one would be chosen from the bunch.
2. **Framework 2 - Adversarial (Tennis) GPDT:** In this version of the framework, two models exist in an adversarial tennis game inspired environment. The model that earns a 'score' is the one that achieves the lowest time complexity within its reasoning nucleus ranked through a test suite of problems. The reason this environment is tennis inspired is because the model has one "safety-net" score, and will stay in competition with the other model as long as it has not lost two rounds in a row. In this version, the simulation can hypothetically go on forever until there is clear winner. A concept drawing of this framework can be found in figure 3. This simulation could lead to exploration of solutions within an unexpected time complexity

if the model happens to perform extremely well. Going back to our time complexity example, this framework would look like a race between two athletes to come up with the best solution. The loser of a round would have only the next round (or more depending on implementer choice) to try and catch up or they would lose. To give the loser better odds at catching up, there could be a reasonome transfer that occurs during their competition, where a HGT like mechanism would transfer reasonome plasmids between models.

3. **Framework 3 - Tournament-Style GPDT:** This framework uses a tournament of the previously mentioned adversarial tennis game environment mentioned above. A concept drawing of this framework can be found in figure 4. Rounds of the adversarial tennis game would play out and the winning model would move onto the next round. The reasonome of the winning (and perhaps all) model(s) included in the tournament can be accessed for further study. A potential extra exploration to be considered could be that the winning model is able to pick up useful reasonomic sequences from its defeated opponent. This additional feature would allow for optimal strategies to accumulate as the models move up the ranks, leading to increased competition and arriving at better solutions. In our time complexity example, this would look similar to the example described in the previous item, but with more rounds (imagine a math tournament with open notes).
4. **Framework 4 - Self-Play Style GPDT:** In this framework, there is once again only one model. This model is its own worst enemy and critic. This model will have a self-reflection mechanism, allowing it to evaluate its current pool of reasonomes and determine if it has indeed converged on an optimal solution. If the model does not think its solution is good enough, it will continue to go through the genetic algorithm cycle of reasonomes described above. This idea would most likely need meta-learning to properly implement. A concept drawing of this framework can be found in figure 5. To put this in terms of our time complexity example, picture a student that will settle for nothing less than a determined score. They are determined and would review their solution multiple times even if it might be 'good' enough to get a passing grade. They would logically follow a line of thinking that would hopefully lead them to converge on the optimal solution. This version of the framework would have to define the model's satisfaction condition, so it does not try to work infinitely towards a goal in a situation where a high or perfect value, like 100% is seemingly impossible.

5 The Potential Implications of GPDT on Human-AI Collaboration

5.1 Evolving Personal Super Intelligence (EPSI)

Recently Meta's Mark Zuckerberg spoke on the idea of personal super intelligence and the hypothetical future that this technology might bring. The CEO talks about a future of human-AI companionship, describing: "AI will improve all our existing systems and enable the creation and discovery of new things that aren't imaginable today". He then goes on to discuss how AI technologies can provide humanity a whole new level of comfort and freedom from certain types of labor, allowing us to focus more on connecting to people (Zuckerberg, 2025). We will use the Meta CEO's vision of 'personal super intelligence' as we discuss our evolving variant. We propose an extension/variant of the idea of personalized super intelligence with evolution concepts used in the GPDT approach. Imagine if not only everyone had access to these personal tools that enhance

the quality of their lives, but if there was a population of these agents capable to sharing ideas through their reasonome. With properly organized population dynamics, we hypothesize that this system would lead to increasing better models, and therefore super intelligent assistance throughout the user-base.

Referring back to our time complexity example, this might look like a wide user base of users working on different math problems. Each model would have it's own reasonome that changes with the problems the user encounters. Perhaps through creating an identical clone of the model and it's reasonome to not interrupt providing the service, all models could be evaluated using meta learning to basically 'farm' the population for better models. An investigation into the reasonome could help plan updates to be spread out to the wider model population's user base. This decentralized approach would allow magnitudes more of combinations to be considered, especially if the model's computer power is mostly dependent on an edge device. This idea could be further extended by integrating the concepts of federated and transfer learning to the synthesis of collective data.

The benefits of this evolving AI system are limited by edge tech it is able to be access from (example: smart phones/glasses). Smart phone's will most likely be the first platform where users would be able to use a mass adaptive version of personalized super intelligence, with smart glasses lagging behind. The bare minimum for a usable smart glasses interface for super intelligence will likely include a microphone allowing for speech interactions with the AI. At the time of writing, there are some commercially available open source headsets that have enough of an interface to implement a basic companion version of this system with EPSI features. However by our current understanding, to fully realize the potential for super intelligent human-AI collaboration there would need to be virtual displays within the lenses easy to use and natural feeling controls. At the time of writing, to our knowledge, this balance of performance and usability has not been achieved.

5.2 Towards Transhumanism

Technologies that enable the parallel process of multiple scenarios could forward the transhumanist efforts long-sought after in science fiction media. **Here are some of our hypothesized uses of parallel deep thinking (genetic or Google's implementation):**

- **Hyper-Learning:** The ability to process multiple knowledge sources at once with AI-enhanced speed would allow one to achieve an unprecedented levels of intelligence. If the information gathered were to be represented in a genomic format (beyond the scope of this paper) and put through a genetic algorithm, one could become a brainstorming master through mixing and matching concepts at incredible speeds.
- **Problem Solving:** As discussed in this paper when going over our time complexity use case for GPDT, parallel processing/consideration of different solutions to problems would greatly decrease the time cost. Applying a genetic element to this transhumanist goal, the AI in the proposed deep thinking team could 'farm' different approaches to get more fit solutions to the problem at hand by mixing and matching the best ones.
- **Strategy:** Extending the problem solving discussion to the world of strategy, deep thinking would allow one to consider the results of all possible actions simulta-

neous given enough compute power. In a game like chess for example, with pre-defined possibilities, they would be essentially unstoppable, especially given the human oversight over the AI within the team unit.

- **Emotional/Social Intelligence:** Applying being a super strategist to conversations, a human-AI team with deep thinking could be a social mastermind by anticipating the results of every potential outcome of a conversation before even speaking a word. That would allow the human-AI deep thinking team to easily get past the guard of nearly anyone, making them to be an expert social climber.

In conclusion, we believe a human-AI team with an agent that possess deep thinking abilities would be intellectually superior to a team without this ability or one that uses a single chain of thought.

5.3 Deep Thinking and the Internet of Things (IoT)

We believe that in the not too distant future, one could use GPDT or other similar deep thinking approaches to monitor and interact with different edge devices. **Here are a few hypothesized applications of Deep Thinking within the IoT domain:**

- **Distributed Diagnostics and Early Warnings (Healthcare):** This would look like wearable sensors on patients with cross analysis with data from thousands to millions of others that are suffering from the same or a similar condition. This would allow for the detection of hidden symptoms, pattern similarities, and detect epidemic level threats. With this proposed system, doctors would be able to provide personalized recommendations back to patients nearly instantaneously.
- **Simulated Patient Profiles (Healthcare):** In this proposed application of GPDT, doctors would be able to consider the outcomes of different treatments in parallel on a virtual patient replica. In theory, compute resources and hospital patient load would be limiting factors in the number of potential treatments a doctor could consider at one time. Using the genetic angle, doctors could merge potential treatments together, and also test those on simulated patients. These systems could be integrated into medical edge devices to allow for the quick synthesis of information to reach quick and correct treatments for patients.
- **Smart Cities (Civil Engineering):** Picture a city where all public utilities are connected and monitored autonomously by AI to ensure that it is functioning smoothly. This is the promise of deep thinking approaches to smart cities. In our hypothesized smart city, things like traffic lights and dispatching of department workers (law enforcement discussed later) would be AI controlled using deep thinking to ensure the best experience for citizens. This system could greatly reduce municipal costs by automating many of the tasks that need to be carried out by administration, freeing them to work on more human oriented tasks. The GPDT approach is relevant here because the system could consider different combinations in simulation that would lead to a more organized city.
- **Precision Farming (Agriculture):** This hypothetical farm would include soil sensors, drones, and weather stations all providing data to an integrated AI system that could control farm behavior through robotics. Integrating a genetic element, a GPDT approach could allow farmers to optimize yields through experimenting

with different crop reproductive strategies. These systems could also consider disease spread and recommend micro-scale interventions (specific land plots, timing, fertilizer mix).

- **Swarm Intelligence (Military/Defense):** Sensors on drones, soldiers, satellites, and vehicles could stream data to a centralized or decentralized system that shares a knowledge base. GPDT could be used to consider the outcomes of different military strategies with enemy responses taken into account. This could provide a military edge to someone that possess such technology.

5.4 Understanding Evolution of Reasoning

Unlike conventional genetic algorithms, which primarily evolve numeric weights or neural architectures, the reasonome operates on discrete, interpretable reasoning modules that resemble functional genes. These modules can be expressed, repressed, mutated, recombined, and horizontally transferred between microbial agents in a simulated environment. This design facilitates the study of both vertical (ancestral) and horizontal (peer-to-peer) transfer of cognitive strategies, echoing the dual inheritance systems observed in natural evolution and cultural transmission. **Key evolutionary phenomena that can be modeled and explored using the Reasoning Genome include:**

- **Emergence of Complex Reasoning:** By tracking the frequency and combination of reasoning operons under varying selection pressures (e.g., time-limited tasks, deceptive environments), researchers can observe how complex reasoning behaviors—such as causal inference or analogical problem-solving—emerge from simpler heuristics.
- **Adaptation to Cognitive Load:** Regulatory regions within the genome allow for conditional expression of reasoning strategies. This enables investigation into how organisms evolve mechanisms to balance cognitive cost with inference precision, paralleling dual-process theories in human cognition.
- **Exaptation and Re-purposing:** Mobile reasoning elements, such as logic transposons or retro-cognitive tags, provide a substrate for studying how cognitive subroutines originally evolved for one task (e.g., analogy in navigation) can be repurposed for others (e.g., social inference), offering insights into cognitive exaptation.
- **Cultural Evolution and Peer Learning:** Through simulated horizontal gene transfer mechanisms, agents can exchange high-performing reasoning modules. This permits controlled studies of cultural evolution dynamics, including the emergence of collective intelligence, distributed reasoning systems, and the propagation of cognitive innovations.

5.5 Cognitive Science Implications

1. **Architecture Optimization:** Replaces hand-engineered cognitive architectures with evolved, adaptive genomes that determine when and how different reasoning modes are activated. This could potentially reduce cognitive engineering effort while increasing robustness and adaptability in real-world environments.
2. **Evolvable Agent Design:** By equipping reinforcement learning agents or embodied robots with a reasonome one could evolve reasoning strategies rather than just

actions or policies. This could enable robots or AI agents to adapt their problem-solving style in new domains, promoting zero-shot or few-shot generalization through reasoning recombination within the reasoning nucleus.

3. **Education and Training:** Intelligent tutoring systems could be built using the GPDT approach and adapt their thinking strategies based on a student's evolving reasoning genome. This would allow for personalized learning by evolving both content and delivery.

5.6 Other Possible Use Cases

1. **Creative Discovery and Scientific Simulation:** The GPDT system could be applied to scientific hypothesis generation. In companion with an automated hypothesis testing environment (like a python interpreter) this could accelerate discovery by evolving reasoning strategies and exploring old ideas through a new lens.
2. **Interpretability Research in AI:** One could use the GPDT approach to study how agent reasoning abilities activate in different contexts. This would increase transparency and traceability of the decision-making process in complex AI systems.
3. **Synthetic Culture and Collective Intelligence:** One could simulate agents in a GPDT system and study the emergence of shared cognitive traditions or cultures, which would provide insight into the way that agents converge on shared inference norms like mathematical thinking or scientific reasoning.

5.7 Potential Dangers

5.7.1 Bio-terrorism

The ability to consider many possibilities at once could be useful in the area of biotechnology. This principal could be used to develop both drugs and toxins. This has already been a growing concern, especially with the increasing availability of open source models where safety checks could perhaps be broken.

5.7.2 Cyber Security

Considering many possibilities at once would also be useful in the cyber security domains. From the angle of the defender of a system, such a technology would allow for an organization to investigate different vulnerabilities all at once. The same on the attacker side is true. This stresses the importance of retaining technological dominance over bad actors within the AI domain.

5.8 Surveillance and Law Enforcement

With incredible deep thinking powers comes great responsibility. A corrupt government could hypothetically use a deep thinking approach to simultaneously keep an eye on all citizens, greatly limiting personal freedoms. Additionally, improper calibration of a genetic addition to this use case could lead to discrimination like focus provided by a models recommendations.

5.8.1 Other Misusage

With the benefits of open source technology also comes the cons. With the availability of models increasing, there runs the risk of someone with the access and intent to cause harm with with these systems. This ethical conundrum is like to perplex law makers as we move forward into the AI age.

5.8.2 Environmental

This proposed system is most likely far off from potentially being able to run smoothing on edge devices given the state of computing infrastructure in 2025. In fact, a system of this level of complexity would likely be very burdensome to the environment in the modern era, as similar existing systems are already doing so.

5.8.3 Ethical Note

Please take into consideration the above notes if one decides to move forward with this concept and weight the pros and cons of the implementation.

6 Next Steps

Here at Grandma's Boy Labs, we believe GPDT is an idea worth investigating thoroughly. Therefore we are planning to setup small Reasonomic experiments within our hardware and compute limitations. This would look something like setting up the simulation environment, building the genome template, define the reasoning mechanism, implement evolutionary mechanics, define metrics of interest, experiment with variants, and analyze the results. Luckily, logic translates well to mathematical and therefore programming languages, so defining these modular units may not be too big of a lift. However, we expect that the most difficult task would be to analyze the results to establish proper initialization parameters due to the non-linear nature of most problems. At the time of writing, we are current just in the planning stage of these experiments but intend to move forward when time and resources are available. We welcome any readers to experiment with their own implementation of Reasonomics if you found this concept interesting.

7 Final Remarks

Our hopes are that this review provided a comprehensive introduction to the concept of Genetic Parallel Deep Thinking 'GPDT' and Reasonomics. We are aware that evolutionary approaches to computation are currently being held back due to their complexity, but here at Grandma's Boy Labs, we believe that evolution is the ultimate automator and could drastically reduce human effort if directed correctly. At the time of submission/writing, experimental plans for testing this concept are on hold for the foreseeable future until an actionable and affordable study protocol can be developed. That being said, if you happen to have the resources to carry out experiment using this concept, we wish you the best of luck and would appreciate being kept in the loop. If you decide to move forward please keep in mind the ethical considerations mentioned in the previous section.

8 Acknowledgments and Dedications

A Appendix

A.1 Plasmid Diagram

Figure 1: Reasonome Capsid Format

A.2 Approach Diagrams

Figure 2: Framework 1

Figure 3: Framework 2

Figure 4: Framework 3

Figure 5: Framework 4

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